

May 2025

LEARN Yellow Paper

Mapping the Education Evidence Base: Unlocking Opportunities to Reduce Educational Inequalities

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DOI for the Yellow Paper: [10.5281/zenodo.15303877](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15303877)

Funding Acknowledgement

This study was supported by the European Commission action HORIZON-CL2-2023-TRANSFORMATIONS-01 for the project LEARN (Longitudinal Educational Achievements: Reducing Inequalities), Grant Agreement 101132531.

Universität
Zürich ^{UZH}

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

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1 ABOUT THE META-REVIEW

The EU Horizon Project LEARN, led by the University of Helsinki, collaborates with partners across Europe, including Manchester Metropolitan University, University College London, Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories (Germany), Maastricht University (Netherlands), universities in Finland (Helsinki and Turku), Switzerland (Zurich and Lausanne), Estonia (Tallinn), Italy (Milan and EU), and Romania (Babeş-Bolyai University). The project aims to map and interpret education evidence and enhance its use in education policy and practice.

LEARN uses a systematic meta-review to rigorously assess the quality of education evidence. This meta-review maps the evidence base of existing reviews of education-focused scientific studies to reveal gaps, such as overlooked educational stages or indicators of inequality. This approach identifies areas needing further research or new perspectives to guide education policy. The LEARN consortium addresses this gap, as part of a broader collective effort to maximise the effectiveness of education research in supporting the use of evidence in policy design. In April 2024, LEARN partners convened, with the aim of catalysing alignment and collaboration and identifying existing education evidence and key questions to explore.

To move forward in their endeavour, LEARN partners first mapped the existing evidence base on educational inequality and socioeconomic disadvantage. To this end, they conducted a systematic meta-review scoping all evidence of socioeconomic disadvantage and educational inequality among children, adolescents, and young adults. The results are presented in a detailed article, which can be accessed on the [EU LEARN website](#) and the [LEARN evidence platform](#) once publicly available.

2 ABOUT THIS YELLOW PAPER

This LEARN Yellow Paper presents key findings from the meta-review. Those interested in the existing body of knowledge about the evidence on educational inequality and socioeconomic disadvantage, evidence coverage, and inequality theory, can see a synthesis of the review findings presented in Section 6. This section showcases a proposed integrated framework, illustrating the main mechanisms, phases, and arenas of inequality.

Alternatively, readers can go straight to Sections 7 and 8, to understand the implications of the existing knowledge, and to see the review's recommendations for stakeholders taking the next steps. Section 7 parses what the meta-review's findings mean for policies designed to reduce educational inequalities and draws out a number of opportunities for driving this endeavour forward. It also presents a set of five learning questions to guide further exploration or a future research agenda. Section 8 then sets out clear, practical recommendations for education experts and policy makers to maximize progress and effectiveness of evidence use in Europe's education policy space.

For the most-time pressed of readers, we recommend the key messages section in section 3. This spotlights what we most want stakeholders to take away from the review; a sense of the quality and coverage of evidence available to them in the education (in-)equality field, and the critical importance – a value – of accessing and building on the wealth of existing knowledge across the interconnected research fields, disciplines, and theoretical perspectives.

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3 KEY MESSAGES

THE OPPORTUNITY

There is a growing urgency to map and interpret existing evidence on educational inequality, as education experts and policymakers show increasing interest in leveraging this knowledge for informed decision-making.

In fact, meta-reviews are a valuable approach across disciplines. They consolidate reviews of numerous studies, offering a comprehensive overview of existing evidence. This approach highlights consistent patterns, gaps, and areas of agreement or debate, providing the expert community with a clearer understanding of complex issues and guiding more effective, evidence-based interventions.

We believe that the science of education and development has a real opportunity not only to reveal existing evidence in education and advance the

SPOTLIGHT

A key finding of this meta-review is that critical educational stages, such as primary and non-university tertiary education, are underrepresented in reviews of the evidence, limiting the scope of our knowledge. Addressing these overlooked stages is crucial to understanding how inequalities develop and persist over time.

Additionally, the analyses revealed a gap between the theoretical depth of educational inequality research and the narrow focus of empirical indicators. While theoretical frameworks like capital theories and

international body of knowledge on educational inequality but also to make a significant contribution to the broader field of evidence-informed policy.

The 2023 Education and Training Monitor report by the European Commission highlighted that efforts to improve access to education and its quality depend on a well-established evidence base, providing a platform for comparative analysis, shared learning, and the exchange of best practices.

Now it is time to map the evidence base – making this the ideal starting point to inform policy design and set the trajectory for research agendas towards under-researched areas in education.

ecological systems are well-developed, empirical studies tend to focus mainly on family-level factors, neglecting broader contexts such as school environments and neighborhood conditions. This disconnect between theory and evidence highlights the need for a broader, more comprehensive evidence base that includes underrepresented stages and wider social contexts. Expanding the evidence base in these areas will support more effective, evidence-driven policymaking, providing a fuller understanding of educational inequality across all phases of a student's development.

4 INTRODUCTION

The meta-review begins by emphasising the need to assess the existing body of knowledge on educational inequalities before moving forward. Educational inequality is a driver of broader societal inequalities, such as income, health, and civic participation, and is rooted in systemic social stratification. Linking this to the more detailed discussion of socioeconomic disadvantage, educational inequality emerges as a process where advantaged families pass on their benefits to their children, reinforcing social stratification.

Socioeconomic status (SES) plays a central role in this process, influencing family dynamics and child development. Indicators like household income, parental education, and occupational class shape educational outcomes, contributing to the systemic differences mentioned earlier. This meta-review focuses specifically on socioeconomic disadvantage, while acknowledging the many intersecting factors contributing to educational inequality. The volatility of household income, particularly during economic instability, further exacerbates educational inequality. The overlap between SES and poverty, with its multidimensional aspects, deepens the social and educational divide, aligning with the earlier point that educational inequality contributes to broader societal disparities.

The LEARN working group in charge of mapping, synthesising, and reviewing education evidence has mapped the evidence base to assess the coverage these reviews have achieved. Their meta-review identifies gaps in evidence related to socioeconomic disadvantage and educational inequality among children, adolescents, and young adults. The objectives are to: (1) systematically scope all relevant evidence syntheses; (2) map review coverage by study count, educational stages, and indicators of disadvantage and inequality; and (3) synthesise conceptual perspectives for a comprehensive interdisciplinary view.

5 METHODOLOGY

A scoping review was chosen for its ability to broadly examine existing literature, identify available evidence, and clarify key concepts in the field of educational inequality and socioeconomic disadvantage. Unlike other systematic reviews, it maps the breadth and scope of research, providing an interdisciplinary synthesis across social sciences and humanities. Only reviews that considered the impact of economic disadvantage on educational inequality were considered. The key inclusion criteria were:

- Socioeconomic status (SES): focus on studies examining the impact of socioeconomic disadvantage on educational inequality.
- Children, adolescents, and young adults: research reviews involving these specific age groups.
- Language: reviews published in English.
- Peer-reviewed articles: only studies that have undergone formal peer review.
- Publication timeline: studies published within the last five years.

To map the shape and scope of the field, synonyms of key concepts (e.g., educational achievement) and search terms were combined using Boolean operators (e.g., AND, OR) to create a search string. For reviews to be considered, they needed to include the term "review" (or synonyms) or "educational achievement" (or synonyms) in the title, and "socioeconomic disadvantage" in the abstract.

Search sites: Web of Science, EBSCO Host, ProQuest, and Scopus databases.

Records were randomly assigned across six members of the research team. Each person screened a third of the records, so that each record was independently screened twice. Researchers conducted a full-text screening of all shortlisted records. Those that met the inclusion criteria were included in the final review. The meta-review comprised 29 reviews that covered 1,950 empirical studies.

6 FINDINGS

The meta-review was premised on the fact that, before LEARN moves forward with efforts to map and interpret existing evidence on educational inequalities, it is important to take stock of the existing body of knowledge.

The core of the meta-review was therefore focused on exploring what is already known about evidence of educational inequalities and socioeconomic disadvantage.

This section summarises of the meta-review's key findings on these topics, synthesised from the meta-review.

6.1 Mapping the Focus of Educational Inequality Reviews

Table 1. Summary of existing knowledge on the socioeconomic gradient in educational inequalities.

Topic	Summary of findings
What types of reviews have been conducted on socioeconomic disadvantage and educational inequality, and what methods were used?	<p>The review emphasizes a focus on systematic narrative methods and reveals a gap in qualitative data synthesis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 29 reviews were conducted, covering 1,950 empirical studies. • 39.93% of the reviews were systematic narrative reviews, that used systematic search methods and a narrative analysis of study findings. • There were 9 meta-analyses and 4 each of scoping and conceptual reviews, with no systematic reviews of qualitative studies, indicating a gap in qualitative data synthesis.
In which academic fields are reviews on educational inequality being published, and what gaps exist in the literature?	<p>The findings reveal a strong focus on educational research, with limited cross-disciplinary engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most reviews (58.62%) were published in educational research journals, with a smaller number in psychology (20.69%) and sociology (10.34%). • Only a few reviews appeared in fields like social policy or medical research, and none in economics, demography, or anthropology, highlighting potential gaps in cross-disciplinary research.
Which educational stages are most commonly studied in single-stage reviews on socioeconomic disadvantage and educational inequality?	<p>The meta-review found a mixed picture in terms of how educational stages are covered in reviews of studies on educational inequality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews focusing on single educational stages were most commonly centred around middle/secondary school (17.24% of reviews) and early years (17.24%). • There were no reviews focused solely on primary education or non-university third-level education (e.g., polytechnic or further education colleges). • University education was represented in 20.69% of single-stage reviews, making it the most studied stage after middle/secondary school.

What is the coverage of multi-stage reviews on educational inequality?	<p>A slightly different picture emerged when looking at reviews covering multiple educational stages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews covering multiple educational stages were more common, with 27.59% of reviews focusing on all school-aged children • A smaller portion of reviews combined early years with all school-aged children (6.90%) or covered all stages from school to university (3.45%). • There was limited coverage of combined middle/secondary and non-university third-level education (3.45%), indicating a gap in research that spans multiple educational stages and, thus, transitions.
What is the coverage of each educational stage across the 29 reviews ?	<p>The meta-review found a gap in research on non-university third-level education, which requires further investigation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middle/secondary school was the most represented stage, accounting for 36.36% of the reviews. • Primary school (25.00%) and university education (18.18%) were also well represented, but non-university third-level education (4.55%) had very little coverage. • Early years education accounted for 15.91% of the reviews.
What are the key indicators of socioeconomic disadvantage ?	<p>Analyses reveal a critical gap in research exploring the wider societal context of educational inequality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews focus heavily on family-level indicators like SES (51.72%), income (34.48%), and parental education (27.59%). • Broader societal factors, such as neighbourhood deprivation and school SES, are underrepresented, each appearing in only 3.45% of reviews.
Which key educational outcomes are studied?	<p>Studies adopting an in equality perspective focus on a few key educational outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic achievement is the most frequently studied outcome, appearing in 55.17% of reviews, mainly measured by grades and test scores. • Educational engagement, including emotional indicators like feelings about learning, and behavioural indicators like student retention and participation, is the second most studied outcome, present in 27.59% of reviews. • Less frequently studied outcomes include cognitive ability, socioemotional skills, and socioeconomic outcomes, each representing only 6.90% of the reviews, highlighting gaps in the exploration of broader developmental and life outcomes, as well as educational mobility and trajectories.

Source: adapted from: Symmonds, J., Chzhen, Y., Kaye, N., Dominey, J., Campbell, C., Sykes, K., Bastug, & I. Fiasconaro, S. (2024): *Educational Inequality and Socioeconomic Disadvantage in Children, Adolescents, and Young People: A Metareview and Conceptual Perspective*. Version_1: submitted to 31/10/2024 to LEARN; in preparation for peer-review.

6.2 Bridging Gaps in Educational Inequality Research Aligning Concepts and Indicators

Table 2: Summary of conceptual perspectives and gaps in reviews.

Topic	Summary of findings
What are the dominant conceptual perspectives in educational inequality research?	<p>Despite the dominance of capital theories across the reviews, critical perspectives on family and psychological development are emerging in the field.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capital accumulation and reproduction theories, especially Bourdieu's social, economic, and cultural capital, dominate across 15 reviews (51.72%). Socioecological and sociocultural development perspectives, including Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory, feature prominently in 8 reviews (27.59%). Family processes and psychological development theories are also key, appearing in 8 reviews (27.59%).
How well do conceptual perspectives align with the indicators of socioeconomic disadvantage?	<p>The mismatch between contextual theories and individual-focused indicators reveals untapped research and policy potential.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conceptual perspectives like ecological and capital theories emphasize the impact of contextual factors on individual development. There is a mismatch between these perspectives and the more individual-focused socioeconomic disadvantage indicators used in the empirical studies (e.g., family income, parental education). Broader contextual indicators, such as classroom composition and neighbourhood deprivation, are underrepresented, despite their relevance to the conceptual frameworks.
Which perspectives are less commonly represented in reviews?	<p>Theoretical perspectives on gender, social structures, and economic processes remain underutilised by reviews.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theories related to gender, cultural processes, life course, and social structures are less prevalent, each appearing in only 3 reviews (10.34%). Economic processes and social mobility are rarely addressed, with only 1-2 reviews including these perspectives.

Source: adapted from: Symmonds, J., Chzhen, Y., Kaye, N., Dominey, J., Campbell, C., Sykes, K., Bastug, & I. Fiasconaro, S. (2024); *Educational Inequality and Socioeconomic Disadvantage in Children, Adolescents, and Young People: A Metareview and Conceptual Perspective*. Version_1: submitted to 31/10/2024 to LEARN; in preparation for peer-review.

6.3 Proposing an Integrated Interdisciplinary Framework

The meta-review presents a comprehensive theoretical synthesis that captures the complexity of educational inequality and socioeconomic disadvantage (listed in Table 3). This framework (illustrated in Figure 1) links theoretical perspectives with empirical evidence and practical applications, emphasizing that educational inequality cannot be confined to a single stage or transition. Instead, it spans across various educational stages, from early childhood through young adulthood, and evolves over time, particularly during key transitions between these stages. The framework underscores the importance of considering both individual and contextual factors in addressing inequality.

Table 3: Summary of conceptual perspectives and gaps in reviews.

Key Features	Description
Multi-stage perspective	Educational inequality is recognized as a dynamic process that unfolds across different educational stages, from early childhood to adulthood.
Emphasis on key transitions	Critical educational transitions, such as moving from primary to secondary education or entering the workforce, are highlighted as moments where inequalities can deepen or shift.
Holistic approach	Both individual-level factors (e.g., family income, parental education) and broader contextual influences (e.g., neighbourhood environments, school quality) are integrated into the analysis.
Interconnectedness	The framework illustrates the relationships between theoretical concepts, empirical findings, and real-world settings and individual characteristics, offering an adaptable tool for researchers and policymakers.
Flexibility in application	While the framework provides a structured approach, it is not rigid and allows for the incorporation of diverse research findings and methodologies to better address the evolving nature of educational inequality.

Source: adapted from: Symmonds, J., Chzhen, Y., Kaye, N., Dominey, J., Campbell, C., Sykes, K., Bastug, & I. Fiasconaro, S. (2024); *Educational Inequality and Socioeconomic Disadvantage in Children, Adolescents, and Young People: A Metareview and Conceptual Perspective*. Version_1: submitted to 31/10/2024 to LEARN; in preparation for peer-review.

7 IMPLICATIONS

This section outlines the main implications of these findings for the education evidence base, and the opportunities to build on, and drive forward the extension of evidence generation and the evaluation of existing evidence.

Understanding What Educational Evidence Measures—and What It Misses Expand Qualitative Evidence in Syntheses

The absence of rich qualitative evidence on socioeconomic educational inequalities in childhood and young adulthood from current syntheses poses a significant limitation. This suggests a need to broaden the type of evidence included in reviews, particularly qualitative studies. Policymakers and academics would benefit from insights that capture lived experiences and contextual nuances. Including qualitative research could offer deeper understanding, especially of how inequalities manifest at various stages of life, enriching the evidence base that informs policies.

Broaden Coverage of Educational Stages

By prioritising **early years and primary education** and broadening the focus to **post-secondary pathways beyond universities**, science can decisively target the root of educational inequalities. Addressing these overlooked stages will close crucial gaps and ensure that evidence **spans every phase of a student's journey**. This approach is key to delivering more impactful, lasting solutions that reshape the landscape of educational equality for future generations.

Widen the Focus Beyond Family-Level Indicators

Future research can **broaden its focus by incorporating indicators like school SES and neighbourhood deprivation**. By expanding beyond family dynamics, we can gain a more comprehensive view of the factors influencing inequality. This will empower policymakers to design more inclusive interventions, addressing the pivotal roles that schools and communities, alongside families, play in shaping educational outcomes.

Diversify Educational Outcomes

Many studies focus narrowly on academic achievement (grades, test scores) and engagement (aspirations, participation), **limiting policy to easily measured outcomes**. To better address educational inequalities, the study of educational inequalities should expand outcomes to **include cognitive ability, academic readiness, social mobility, and socioemotional skills**. This broader approach would provide a fuller picture of student success and support more nuanced policy design.

Aligning Perspectives with Research Practice for Better Evidence-informed Policies

Align Conceptual Perspectives and Indicators

Aligning advanced conceptual perspectives with broader, context-based indicators is essential for unlocking a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of educational inequality.

Future research needs to use broader indicators that reflect the different social contexts influencing educational inequality, such as school environments, peer networks, and cultural settings. For more accurate insights and more effective policy responses, **it is crucial to align conceptual perspectives and empirical indicators**.

Toward a Unified Perspective on Inequalities in Education

The 66 conceptual frameworks documented across the 29 reviews highlight the complexity of educational inequality. This diversity underscores the need for a new interdisciplinary perspective. By integrating insights from sociology, psychology, economics, and education, we comprehensively understand how factors interact, driving more effective, targeted interventions.

Figure 1. An Integrated Interdisciplinary Perspective (IIP) on Educational Inequality and Socioeconomic Disadvantage in CAYA.

Source: adapted from: Symmonds, J., Chzhen, Y., Kaye, N., Dominey, J., Campbell, C., Sykes, K., Bastug, & I. Fiasconaro, S. (2024): Educational Inequality and Socioeconomic Disadvantage in Children, Adolescents, and Young People: A Metareview and Conceptual Perspective. Version_1: submitted to 31/10/2024 to LEARN; in preparation for peer-review.

Meta-reviews act as a powerful lens

Research on educational inequalities still prioritises educational outcomes that are easy to measure, narrowing the policy viewpoint to those outcomes.

Meta-reviews act as a powerful lens, a) mapping the evidence base, making this the ideal starting point to inform policy design and set the trajectory for research agendas towards under-researched areas in education, and b) revealing synergies between strands of research to form a more comprehensive picture of educational inequality.

Box 1: Big five learning questions for further exploration:

Based on the insights from this meta-review, the analysis suggests five key learning questions for further exploration in addressing educational inequality:

1. How do different social contexts, such as school environments, neighbourhoods, and peer networks, feature the measurement of socioeconomic disadvantage in education? And, similarly, how can researchers better incorporate these broader indicators into empirical studies and policy frameworks?
2. What is the impact of integrating interdisciplinary perspectives (e.g., sociology, psychology, and economics) on both a) the quality of research and b) the effectiveness of policies designed to reduce educational inequality? Does this interdisciplinary approach yield more comprehensive outcomes?
3. How do specific interventions, designed with broader socioecological perspectives in mind, influence long-term educational outcomes and societal mobility across various stages of education (from early childhood to tertiary levels)?
4. What role can institutions play in expanding research on underrepresented educational stages and indicators of inequality? What are the challenges related to funding priorities, power dynamics, and the scalability of results?
5. How does the alignment (or lack thereof) between theoretical frameworks and empirical indicators evolve over time in this field? Can a more systematic synthesis of these frameworks lead to lasting institutional changes in how educational inequality is researched and addressed?

8 RECOMMENDATIONS

This section summarises two sets of recommendations presented within the review for researchers and policy makers respectively.

For Researchers

These three critical actions will help researchers to advance the evidence-base:

Expand Coverage Across Educational Stages: Future research should focus on underrepresented stages, particularly primary and non-university tertiary education. Addressing these critical phases show how inequalities develop and persist throughout a student's educational journey.

Broaden the Scope of Indicators: Researchers should move beyond family-level indicators like parental income and education to include broader contextual factors, such as school SES, neighbourhood deprivation, and peer networks. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of educational inequality.

Adopt Interdisciplinary Approaches: Researchers are encouraged to synthesise insights more broadly from sociology, psychology, economics, and other related fields to develop more holistic models. By integrating these perspectives, the field can better capture the complexity of educational inequality and generate more effective policy solutions.

For Policy Makers and Education Experts

These three critical actions will help policy makers and education experts to advance the evidence-base:

Address the Evidence Gaps in Educational Stages: Invest in rigorous evaluations of underrepresented educational stages, such as primary and non-university tertiary education, to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of where inequalities arise and persist.

Dedicate Resources for Systematic Review and Knowledge Sharing: Allocate sufficient resources to document, evaluate, and share insights from existing educational research, using a systematic monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) approach.

Package and Disseminate Evidence to Address Gaps: Ensure that findings from reviews and research on educational inequality are packaged and shared to fill existing gaps. This should include operational insights on policy design and broader lessons on systemic impacts. Learning should be communicated through various formats, both practical reports and academic publications, and translated into multiple languages to support regional policy communities globally.

Promote Flexibility in Policy Approaches: Be adaptive and responsive to emerging evidence, allowing for flexible approaches in policy design and implementation that can evolve over time based on new insights.

Leverage Existing Evidence in Policy Design: Commit to integrating existing research evidence into policy and program design, ensuring that policies are rooted in the best available knowledge on educational inequality.

Strengthen Communication and Engagement Strategies: Invest in comprehensive communication and engagement strategies at both global and local levels to ensure that the findings from educational research contribute to the broader evidence-informed policy ecosystem, including sectors beyond education.

9 CONCLUSION

This Yellow Paper, based on the extensive meta-review of educational inequality research, highlights significant opportunities for policymakers to better leverage scientific evidence in addressing socioeconomic disparities in education. Despite the wealth of research available, there are striking gaps in the coverage of critical educational stages and broader socioeconomic indicators, which limit the scope of current evidence.

A few multi-stage reviews have examined students across **key educational transitions**, providing insights into how inequalities develop over time. This evidence is crucial for policymakers, as a **life-course perspective** reveals critical stages where targeted interventions can effectively alter trajectories, reducing inequality in the long term. By adopting these findings, policymakers can leverage the full scope of existing knowledge to create strategic, evidence-informed policies that address educational inequality comprehensively and sustainably.

The review underscores the urgent need to expand the focus of research **beyond family-level indicators**, integrating school, community, and neighbourhood contexts to create more comprehensive policy interventions. Moreover, it reveals the importance of developing a more interdisciplinary approach that synthesises insights from sociology, psychology, and economics to address the complexity of educational inequality.

Investing in more rigorous, context-sensitive research can significantly improve the use of evidence in policy design. This investment has the potential to drive transformative change, ensuring that education systems around the world are equipped to address inequalities from an early stage and throughout students' educational journeys. By embracing these opportunities, policymakers can advance evidence-based strategies that ultimately contribute to more equitable and effective education systems for all learners globally.

We see a unique moment to bridge gaps in the evidence base and to promote policies that are not only informed by research but also capable of driving meaningful change in reducing educational inequalities.

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